

Public Relations Strategies in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study focuses on public relations strategies in the tourism and hospitality industry in Cross River State, Nigeria. The paper explores public relations strategies that are essential for building brand image, fostering trust, and promoting growth through marketing communication to boost tourism and hospitality industries using effective strategies that include developing a positive destination, engaging in transparent crisis communication, and building relationships with potential tourists. The study is anchored in social exchange theory, which proposes two-way relationships between organisations and publics. It utilizes public relations strategies to influence attitudes and actions of key stakeholders. This study employs a qualitative research method. Data was collected through focus groups organised around specific themes. The findings reveal that there is a significant lack of public relations and marketing strategies from both operators and government entities. Additionally, public relations strategic efforts for the tourism and hospitality industry in Cross River State have been insufficiently implemented, with no sustainable strategies in place for tourism marketing in the state over the past eight years. The paper concludes that public relations should be leveraged as a key marketing strategy for the Cross River State tourism and hospitality industry as public relations activities and strategies provide valuable reward to the public. The study recommends that tourism and hospitality should be enhanced to boost overall tourist satisfaction. The Cross River tourism industry should focus on improving public relations and strategic marketing, which plays a key role in promoting responsible travel and highlighting a destinations commitment to the environment. This involves Transcorp's hotel integrating these elements to attract and retain visitors through compelling public relations messages that motivate

action. Creating publicity through various channels is used to make products, services, and destinations more visible to tourists.

Keywords: Public relations, strategies, tourism, hospitality, industry, marketing, promotion.

Introduction

Public relations have great importance in hospitality. Public relations in hospitality involve managing communication with stakeholders, such as the public, media relations, clients, and investors, by successfully interacting with these stakeholders, PR aims to develop and maintain a favorable reputation and connection with its internal and external. Public relations in the hospitality industry are responsible for promoting brands and maintaining their reputation. PR also helps increase awareness of hospitality services to potential clients. To achieve its goals, PR experts employ a range of strategies that include media relations, social media management, crisis communication, event planning, and community engagement.

According to Yang, Silva, and Barlow (2017), hospitality have several management functions to help operate at maximum capacity: research and development, finance, legal, human resources, marketing, and operations. Asemah, Josiah, and Adeline (2020), observed that no formal business organisation is an island, each exists within a framework of interrelated systems of relationships with key stakeholders.

According to Scott, Allen, and Glen (2022), public relations' unique function is to help the business develop and maintain relationships with all its key publics and stakeholders by effectively communicating with these groups. Communication is key in maintaining satisfactory, long-term, trusting relationships with publics and stakeholders. Yet, without efficient transmission, these systems as enunciated by these scholars cannot be effective. Therefore, the efficient transmission of communication signals, which we refer to here as public relations strategies, is the mainstay of this study.

Asemah *et al* (2020) affirms that public relations is a vital subsystem of the hospitality industry and organisation. The effective practice of public relations is integrally bound to the growth of a business. Okoi, and Agba (2023, p. 47), Public relations are thought of as communication and action on the part of a business that supports development and maintenance of mutually beneficial relationships between the business and the groups with which it is interdependent. Meanwhile, public relations strategies in the hospitality industry are a necessity to enhance business growth and ensure proper image and goodwill (Fitch & L'Etang 2017).

Egbulefu and Nwaoboli (2023), describe public relations as any form of communication which is aimed at bringing about goodwill and mutual understanding between an organisation and its publics. This is because every business organisation needs to create a favourable image for itself before its internal and external publics for successful operation. Through effective public relations, a business organisation will be able to win public acceptance (Greco 2019).

According to Asemah (2009, p. 249), public relations is considered a two-way communication between an organisation and the audience critical to its success. Asemah (2009), further describes public relations as an activity geared towards the construction of positive image or reputation for an organisation and influences attitudes of the people towards a brand. It suffices

to state that public relations are responsible for the creation of favourable attitudes among key audiences. Kotler (2016), points that as a function of management, it is primarily responsible for shaping and implementing policies of mediation, among socio-political and economic interests, which could influence the growth, survival and development of the hospitality industries.

Okoi, Obukoadata, and Ebia (2021, p.100), Public relations are essential to the hospitality sector since they assist in creating and preserving a favorable public perception of the industry, hotel, restaurant, or any other hospitality firm. Having a solid public relations plan is crucial for success of hospitality. Public relations may contribute to the development of a positive reputation and the fostering of enduring connections that foster corporate growth and success, whether through the media, social media, or community engagement. To attract and retain customers, it is essential to maintain relationships with customers, staff, the media, and other stakeholders that may be cultivated and strengthened with the aid of public relations.

Hence, the primary objective of public relations practitioners is to cultivate a robust corporate image, brand recognition and reputation, by means of strategic public relations endeavors. This can raise customer satisfaction and eventually boost income.

Statement of the Problem

Succeeding in the hospitality industry is a difficult task that needs effective strategies. Strategies that can help boost and promote the goals of the organisation.

This practical application is found in public relations activities and its theoretical framework within the hospitality industry. Public relations strategies for hospitality in Cross River state are crucial. They involve promotional activities and communications of the hospitality industry and their unique product through strategic communication and integrated marketing strategies such as social media, digital sales, sales promotion and advertising. The goal for any hospitality industry is to deliver high quality service to its guests, increase business capabilities and expand its reach to achieve growth, and financial stability, while maintaining profitability.

In recent years, particularly over the last three years, significant concerns have emerged among stakeholders in the tourism and hospitality sectors in Cross River State which includes a lack of strategic planning, insufficient maintenance of infrastructure, inadequate funding and support, sustainability in events and lack of effective strategy communication system to promote the sector. This has led to a notable decline in tourist traffic observed, raising alarms about tourism and hospitality in Cross River State.

However, owners and managers of the hospitality industry seem not to have come to terms with the significance of public relations. The hospitality industry needs to come to the terms that public relations strategies, if effectively used may lead to many of them recording significant in patronage; loyal publics; financial impact; customers' satisfaction; profit margin; increased revenue. To achieve all this, hospitality organisations need a satisfactory public relations strategy. To understand fully the public relations strategies in the hospitality industry, Transcorp's hotel was selected for the study because it is at the central core of hospitality industry in Cross River state.

Objectives of the Study

- i. Ascertain the significance of public relations strategies in the tourism and hospitality industry in Cross River State.
- ii. Determine the various public relations tools and strategies used in Transcorp's hotel Calabar.
- iii. Identify best practices for effective public relations in the tourism and hospitality industry.

It is expected that through this study, the public relations practitioners would make efforts towards building a reputable local and international image for their business. The outcome of this research would further make the managers of the hospitality industries and business managers in Cross River State, Nigerian, use more of public relations strategies in their businesses.

Literature Review

Hospitality Industries

Within a nation's economy, there are many industries to grow and develop the nation. Sectors such as agriculture industries, manufacturing industries etc. Kotler (2016) posits that hospitality industries are service industries that provide tangible services to satisfy the customer.

According to United Nations World Tourism Organisation, media reporting is significant to hospitality and tourism because most travel decisions are made by people who have never seen the destination firsthand for themselves (UNWTO, 2007).

The hospitality industry has finally embraced marketing concepts that other industries have been using successfully for decades. Marketing is a very important matter in hospitality, travel and tourism industry as it is the most important management influence that can bring the size and behaviour into the foremost tourism market. Theoretically, public relations strategy is useful to improve poor relations and build relationships which occurred because of several unfortunate marketing events (Kotler, 2016).

Areas of Hospitality

The main objective of the hospitality industry is to focus on high -quality customer base. Providing quality service and a memorable experience. Kotler (2016, p. 249), listed out three main areas of the hospitality industry to include: accommodations (hotels), food and beverage (restaurants, fast food), and travel and tourism (airlines, destinations).

All areas of hospitality focus on the customer. Scott et al, (2022), emphasized that in the hospitality industry, public relations are more than a necessity. To meet the constant challenges, the public relations in the hospitality industry should evolve towards turning into a management function, which should lead to responsible approach. According to specialists, cultivating public relations takes longer, but when they are actuated, they can contribute to promoting the company on the market (Asemah 2011; Kotler 2016; & Scott *et al*, 2022).

The Concept of Public Relations

There are many definitions of public relations which have created some form of misconception, but nonetheless, some basic parameters always help avail us with a frame with which we can conceptualize the concept

Public relations is one of the promotional tools that have gained importance in brand promotion, especially with its effectiveness building business organisations and increasing credibility, customers loyalty. In other words, it establishes cordial and fruitful relationship between an organisation and its publics, including directors, customers, suppliers, bankers, creditors, shareholders, community leaders, media, top management officials and agencies.

Public relations are a management function which helps in establishing a favourable relationship between an organisation and its public (Orlando & John 2014). Scott, et al, (2022), emphasized the various activities handled by the public relations department include: conflict resolution or crisis management, internal or employee relations, community relations, promotions, media relations, and sponsorship programmes. Public relations are acknowledged to be very vital to the survival of business organisations, institutions and individuals.

Orlando and John (2014), opines that since public relations functions are all about creating mutual understanding through information and communication, as well as, monitoring, relationships, and reputation management, and maintaining effective working environment within the business organisation through employee communication, and seeking to maintain mutual understanding with its internal and external publics for harmonious coexistence can no longer be overemphasized.

Asemah et al, (2020), argues that public relations which is the most valuable asset of a business is uniquely placed to identify and understand the needs and expectations of the business organisation's environment such as those related to the business through decision-making processes to generate a response or action that meets the combined needs of the organisation and its environment. Hence, the most effective business strategy to manage its publics for development is through public relations strategies.

Public relations strategies are relevant marketing tools that businesses can use to attract and persuade customers to the organisations. Through the integration of communication tools such as advertising, sales promotion, social media, digital marketing, businesses lay a major emphasis on building relationships based on trust and loyalty.

The Public Relations Functions

The categorization of specialist jobs in public relations involves establishing connections and making appeals to certain publics to foster understanding and acceptance of specific policies, procedures, individuals, causes, commodities, and services (Egbulefu & Nwaoboli 2023). The main duties of public relations are the establishment and maintenance of favourable connections with both the internal and external audiences of an organisation or business. These publics sometimes referred to as the stakeholders of the company encompass a wide range of entities, including people, commercial organisations, governmental bodies, and social groups.

The primary objective of public relations in a business is to facilitate the establishment of credibility and confidence among customers. They not only contribute to the enhancement of information pertaining to the business, but also allow it the chance to establish, regulate, and distribute its message to individuals both within and externally to the company.

Public relations functions are effective in promoting business, facilitating communication during a crisis, and safeguarding the business reputation against media attacks (Zeithaml, & Bitner 2000). In business organisations, trust, and value are mainly gained from reputation. Hence, Scott

et al. (2022) argues that reputation of a business is the most asset. By implication, businesses consider maintaining the relationship between their clients the most vital. Research has shown that public relations functions are of essential and the ultimate significance when it comes to marketing or promoting a brand.

Asemah *et al.* (2022) emphasized the significance of public relations functions to include positive reputation, fostering trust and credibility, that enhances awareness among individuals by providing information on the product specifications and the fundamental principles of the business.

Hence, the most effective hospitality strategies to a successful development are through the extensive use of public relations strategies. Egbulafu and Nwaoboli (2023) states that public relations is a strategic managerial process which must be involved in the process when developing strategies for building and maintaining business. Public relations as a strategy can clearly increase economic value for businesses because it creates brand awareness through the relevant marketing strategies, businesses can easily attract customers to the company.

The use of Public Relations in Hospitality Industries

In any hospitality industry, trust plays a pivotal role in growing and developing the business. Lack of trust and value can lead to loss of sales. Hence, to increase credibility in business and have the desired outcome by improving organisation's reputation is through the various use of public relations strategies that educate and inform the customers about the organisation and enhance brand recognition, making it more visible in the public domain. Yang *et al.* (2017) emphasizes that using public relations strategies, the company can monitor the interests of its consumers, partners, investors, and employees, identify threats, and help management to resolve various conflicts. In case of any dispute, they can take action to establish a dialogue quickly. The focus of public relations is public opinion.

Public relations have become an essential part of hospitality industry. It influences the performance of tourism and hospitality marketing strategies. Thus, as Scott *et al.* (2022) rightly states, for better opportunities and outcomes, collaborating with a well-established public relations agency is more than just essential to stand out from the competition. Selda, and Betül (2014) observed three functions of public relations in business development as:

Public Relations Enhance Hospitality Industry Visibility and Awareness

Public relations promote brand visibility in a crowded marketplace, where brands are competing for their customers' attention, Public Relations may be able to direct the spotlight of the brand at the timely moment.

Public relations influences and shapes the desired narrative about the brand by using a blend of public relations tactics including but not limited to publicity and media relations, content creation, influencer partnerships, event management, online presence management, and awards, to enhance the brand's visibility and help a brand reach new markets and target audiences, expanding its customer base and business opportunities.

Public Relations Establish Trust, Credibility and Value

Every business trust, credibility, and value are the bedrock upon which successful businesses are built. Public Relations emerges as the steadfast guardian, wielding its strategic prowess to establish unwavering trust, credibility, and value with customers. At its core, the role of public relations is to shape the perception of a brand among stakeholders. Through various skillful efforts such as storytelling, thoughtfully crafted messages, and genuine authenticity, public relations strive to weave a narrative that resonates deeply with target audience. By consistently delivering transparent and compelling communications, public relations build a foundation of trust that forms the very essence of brand identity. As trust cannot flourish without credibility and when there is credibility, then there is value. Hence, public relations help to maintain long-term relationships with media representatives, securing opportunities for brands to be featured in reputable publications and online platforms. By positioning brand as an authoritative voice and imparting an aura of expertise and reliability that deeply resonates with clients, employees, investors, and suppliers.

Public Relations Contain Crisis in the Hospitality Industry

In the unpredictable landscape of business, crises can strike out, threatening reputations can plug the organisation into turmoil. For this reason, public relations may play a vital role in managing crises and mitigating reputational damage. As a crisis typically strikes at the worst possible moment, swift and effective communication becomes paramount. Fortunately, public relations strategies can be used in crisis management.

Public relations strategies have become the voice of reason and reassurance during turbulent times by helping to stabilize situations and restore trust amidst uncertainty. In the digital era, where news spreads like wildfire across social media platforms, public relations play a vital role in monitoring and managing online conversations during a crisis. By actively engaging with stakeholders, addressing concerns, and providing transparent updates, public relations helps contain the spread of negative sentiment and counteracts potential reputational damage caused by viral misinformation or negative public sentiment.

Theoretical Framework

The Social Exchange Theory (SET)

The theory developed by Thibault and Kelley in 1952 explains why, and how a two-way persuasive communication can promote relationship (Ogbuoshi 2020).

- i. Every interaction involves an exchange: goods or services.
- ii. People try to get from others as much as they have given to them.

Social exchange theory explains how we feel about a relationship with another person, depending on our perception of the balance between what we put into the relationship and what get out of it; the kind of relationship we deserve, the chances of having a better relationship with someone else.

The social exchange theory is relevant to this study because it helps explain how people evaluate the costs and benefits of relationships. It suggests that maintaining long-term relationships in business requires continuously evaluating the costs and benefits for both parties. These theories can be used to understand customers' needs and adapt new strategies for business development.

Methodology

The study utilized a qualitative research methodology, incorporating a projective policy-based technique to delve into the subconscious reasoning and emotions of PR managers, employee and government tourism and hospitality industry in Cross River State. This conforms to Ogbuoshi's (2020), position that, qualitative method enables the researcher to study patterns in behaviour without being bias or judgmental in a situation under investigation.

Population of the Study and Sampling Selection Procedure

The study comprised of selected participants and stakeholders ranged from tourist practitioners, and officials of the Cross River State Tourism Bureau and Promotion Commission (public relations managers) with over seven (7) years post tourism and hospitality working experience.

The reliance on FGDs was driven by the need to gather insights from a specialized population on a topic of professional interest. Although the exact population size was not predetermined, a sample size of 10 participants was established, aligning with Creswell's (2015) recommendation that qualitative studies typically require a sample size of 10 to 36. This sample was divided into two FGDs, each consisting of five participants (D1 and D2). The composition of the groups included four tourist practitioners and six personnel from the Tourism Bureau and Promotion Commission. Participants were selected based on their direct involvement in hospitality activities over the years, without bias toward gender, age, or qualifications; selection was based solely on knowledge and participation in the event. During reporting, participants were labeled as D1a, D1b, D1c, D1d, and D1e for the first FGD, and D2a, D2b, D2c, D2d, and D2e for the second FGD. The data collected were analyzed thematically.

Results

Theme 1: Exploring what is the significance of public relations strategies in the tourism and hospitality industry

Discussion among the participants illuminated several specific strategies through which public relations can be effectively employed in the strategic marketing of hospitality industry Cross River State. The PR manager agreed that public relations usage in strategic marketing and promotion of hospitality is of high influence on the destination. For instance, when asked whether they use public relations as one of their promotional strategies participant D1a said: *"we use personal sales to interact with our customers."* In the words of participant D1b: *"we use social media since we often have our clients come to us."* The response from participant D1c: was that *"yes we use more of face-to-face interaction with our customers because we can easily reach them here and promote our services from what they see."* The response from participant D2a: was that *"because we can easily reach tourists on social media, we use marketing to promote our services from what they see."* The response from participant D2b: was that *"we use sales promotion because in tourism and hospitality the aims is to influence potential tourists to choose their specific destination."* The response from participant D2c: was that *"in tourism it is crucial for tourism and*

hospitality industry to understand the effectiveness of using public relations to strategically persuade potential tourists.”

Data obtained from the (FGDs), were used to achieve the goals of objectives one reveal that the participants in study use sales promotion strategies in their tourism destinations. They indicate that they use more face-to-face interaction strategies in promoting their business. Also, they indicated that their sales promotion strategies are more to them like public relations. The consensus revealed that while tourism and hospitality industry utilizes various advertising techniques, these methods often lack a systematic approach. It is crucial to differentiate between marketing concepts and other advertising tools, as advertising serves as a vital component of the broader marketing mix. The marketing of tourism is inherently a collective and collaborative endeavour, integrating elements of public relations, marketing, advertising, publicity, and persuasive communication (Okoi, Obukoadata, & Ebia, 2021).

The discourse underscored that the successful integration of public relations within strategic marketing frameworks is essential for establishing a robust marketing structure (Asemah, Josiah, & Adeline 2020), for hospitality industry. It was emphasized that hospitality, as an industry, requires dedicated attention to public relations strategies to enhance its appeal to the public and foster growth.

We can say that the findings from the discussion indicate that public relations strategies for tourism and hospitality can yield substantial benefits. By adopting a more structured and cohesive public relations and marketing strategy that leverages the strengths of various advertising channels, including social media thereby contributing to the overall growth and sustainability of tourism.

Theme 2: What is the effectiveness of the various public relations tools and strategies used in Transcorp’s hotel Calabar?

In the words of participant D1d: *“the strategic marketing of the Transcorp’s hotel is effective because of the nature of marketing strategies used in some form of public relations which is quite effective.”* The response from participant D1e: *“although public relations strategies are effectively used in tourism that includes using persuasive language to creating influence and appeal to emotions in building trust, and the connections needed.”* In the words of participant D2d: was that *“we mostly explore advertising strategies using online platforms, personal sales for marketing and public relations.”* In the words of participant D2e: was that *“In today’s world, characterized by an emphasis on experiences, experiential integrated marketing communication has emerged as a powerful approach that prioritizes the customer’s direct engagement with a brand over traditional marketing techniques that target a broad audience.”* In the words of participant D1a: was that *“Marketing of our tourism and hospitality destination mostly the Calabar needs to be persuasive in nature because its needs transparency and truthfulness that would avoid misleading advertising.”*

Data from the above response shows that although the participants use more of persuasive communication based on their market structure. However, their responses indicate that public relations, advertising, and personal sales strategies have been effectively used.

At its core, strategic communication involves meticulous planning and management aimed at achieving specific goals within the marketing framework. This process is essential for marketers, as it enables them to develop a synchronized communication strategy that effectively reaches

diverse market segments with a unified message. To realize this objective, the communication employed must be inherently persuasive, utilizing the appropriate methodologies to foster a favourable climate for promoting the destination while simultaneously informing and educating potential tourists about the unique offerings of the Cross River destinations (Egbulefu, & Nwaoboli. 2023).

Theme 3: To what extent is utilization of public relations strategies in boosting effective public relations in the hospitality industry?

In response to the above question, the participants affirmed that the utilization of public relations strategies in boosting effective public relations in the tourism and hospitality industry is most suitable. The discussions reached a consensus in line with Egbulefu, and Nwaoboli. 2023), Okoi, *et al* 2021),

Participate D1b said: *“yes public relations are recognized as one of the most significant components of an effective marketing strategy within the tourism and hospitality sector. The participant emphasized that tourists are often influenced by the credibility and trustworthiness of the information they encounter, which is typically conveyed through various content mediums.”* In the words of participate D1c said: *“public relations is a prominent strategy identified for persuading tourists to any destination marketing. To attracts travelers to a specific locale, it is essential to highlight and maintain the unique attributes of that destination.”*

In response, participate D2a: *“revealed that there is a clear desire among tourists to visualize their potential destinations before making travel decisions, indicating that effective marketing should provide vivid representations of what awaits them.”* Participate D2b said: *“Yes, destination marketing, is not merely about promoting a location; it involves positioning it as superior to alternative options by emphasizing its distinctive qualities and the experiences it offers through public relations strategies.”*

In response, participate D2c said: *“yes, for us to have successful destination marketing we create a narrative that showcases the uniqueness of our hospitality, illustrating the cultural richness, vibrant festivities, and engaging activities that define the event.”*

In response, participate D1e said: *“yes, public relations and strategic marketing are effective in boosting effective public relations in the hospitality industry because its appeal to emotions of tourists and attracts them to the destination.”*

In conclusion, the discussions highlighted that the intersection of public relations, content marketing, and destination marketing is crucial for the marketing of Cross River State tourism and hospitality industry. By leveraging these approaches, stakeholders can create compelling narratives that resonate with tourists, ultimately enhancing the attractiveness of the destinations and fostering a deeper connection between visitors and the rich cultural tapestry of Cross River State.

Conclusion

The Cross River tourism and hospitality industry has significantly overlooked the critical role of public relations in its marketing strategies, a factor that is essential for attracting a larger influx of tourists to the Cross River State. To enhance tourism appeal in the state, the industry must adopt a comprehensive strategy of integrated communication mix, that effectively integrates public relations, advertising, and marketing communication practices. This integration is vital, especially as other regions are rapidly developing unique tourist destinations that compete for the attention of potential visitors.

The Cross River tourism and hospitality industry must acknowledge and harness the substantial growth potential that exists within the state. The sluggish pace of development can largely be attributed to egocentric approaches and outdated press agency strategies that fail to resonate with modern audiences. To meet the ambitious tourism benchmarks set by the State Government for 2030, it is essential to embrace public relations, persuasive communication and strategic marketing techniques. These methodologies are not merely supplementary; they are fundamental to attracting new tourists while simultaneously retaining the loyalty of existing visitors.

The marketers responsible for the hospitality industry, particularly Transcorp's hotel Calabar, must recognize that to fulfill their mandate within Cross River State, they need to weave public relations and strategic marketing strategies into their operations. These techniques should function as the veins and arteries that transport vital information and engagement from the "heart" of tourism to the broader system, facilitating a dynamic exchange based on mutual understanding. By doing so, they can better align the interests of destinations with those of tourists, effectively bridging the credibility gap that currently exists.

This is a pivotal moment for the Cross River tourism and hospitality industry. It is essential to take decisive action and implement these necessary changes to revitalize the sector. By embracing a more strategic approach to marketing and communication, the industry can significantly enhance its ability to attract a diverse array of tourists, thereby ensuring the long-term sustainability and growth of tourism and the broader tourism landscape in Cross River State.

Recommendations

- i. There is a great need for the hospitality industry to have public relations strategies. Understanding that public relations functions have impact on service delivery.
- ii. To build business reputation and get value, trust and credibility, public relations strategies are important to influence the market by sending persuasive messages to publics about their service delivery create high level satisfaction.
- iii. To enhance tourism and hospitality appeal and boost overall tourist satisfaction, the Cross River tourism industry should focus on improving public relations and strategic marketing. This involves Transcorp's hotel integrating these elements to attract and retain visitors through compelling public relations messages that motivate action.

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